

INVESTIGATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TOW STEERED CFRP PANELS

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SUMMARY

As an automated preforming technique, tow steering offers excellent opportunity to tailor preforms. However, inherent limitations of this technique include in-plane and through-thickness presence of stitch yarn, backing fabric and a stitch-heavy side of the preform. A soluble stitch yarn and a peel-ply are used to overcome these limitations.

KEYWORDS: Tow Steering, Preform, Static Mechanical Properties

INTRODUCTION

Tow steering and placement using an embroidery machine has been around for more than a decade. Developed in Germany, in the mid 1990s, this technique uses a stationary embroidery head which stitches a single carbon tow or a glass roving on to a thin substrate to provide localised in-plane and through-thickness reinforcement [1]. This technology, also known as Tailored Fibre Placement, uses a pre-determined fibre path designed, using suitable software, to accommodate the loading experienced by a fibre reinforced polymer composite. Fig. 1 shows the tow steering unit, where a stitching head, a numerically controlled frame (with x-y movement) and a steering unit (with 360° movement) are used to orient fibres according to the designed path. Further details of the machine and the design variables are described elsewhere [2].

A number of published papers have dealt with design and application of tow steered composite parts and reported coupon level mechanical properties. Some of the early work by Feltin and Gliesche [3, 4], Corthers et al [5, 6] introduced the tow steering technique which can be used to tailor the anisotropic behaviour of fibre reinforced composites to design and build a number of products. Mattheij et al [7] were the first to report the mechanical properties of UD and cross-ply tow steered carbon-epoxy and glass-epoxy composites. They found through static and fatigue testing that tow steered panels achieve significantly lower mechanical properties compared to those of prepreg, but fared well against woven fabrics. They indicated that these reductions in properties are due to the resin rich zones in the base material and around the stitching yarn; and fibre waviness caused by the in-plane stitching yarn. Feltin and Gliesche [8] reported good in-plane properties for UD glass-epoxy; UD and cross-ply carbon-epoxy (PR 500) tow steered panels.

Mattheij et al [9] also investigated cross-ply and quasi-isotropic carbon-epoxy tow steered panels containing various stitching yarns. Their investigation showed the

importance of selecting ideal stitch density and stitching yarn tension to achieve a good balance of reduced in-plane properties and increased out-of-plane properties. They reported better fracture toughness and compression after impact (CAI) strength properties of tow steered panels compared to prepregs. Rolfes et al [10] and Temmen et al [11] described a design tool TACO (Tailored Composite Design Code) which they developed to produce parts using tow steering. They reiterated the local spatial variations in the tow steered preform and indicated that compression strength of tow steered panels vary between 40-70% of prepreg properties, mainly due to the introduction of crimp and fibre damage during preform production.

Fig. 1: Tow Steering Unit

Gliesche et al [12] and Breuer [13] found the additional deposition of tow around a hole a good method to reduce the stress concentration in that region. Similar improvements were reported by Tosh and Kelly [14] who used manual tow steering and by Mills et al [15] who again used manual method but a binder-coated tow. Weimer et al [16], however, reported poor open-hole tensile and pin-loaded bearing strengths of tow steered samples caused due to the interfacial weakness in the patch between the tow steered and NCF fabrics.

In another design case, buckling behaviour of a tailored compression loaded plate, produced using a variable stiffness concept proposed by Gurdal [17], has been studied in great detail by a number of researchers [18-21]. However, all those works were based on the use of tow steering of prepregs and not dry fibre. Production of such a panel using an embroidery technique requires consideration of the decrease in aspect ratio of the steered fibre in a curvilinear path, stitch yarn variables, and the stitch heavy backing fabric. Some of these inherent limitations of tow steering technique using embroidery were pointed out by Meyer [22] recently.

In the current study the latter two limitations were eliminated by using a commercially available phenoxy yarn, soluble in epoxy resin. Using a novel method it was possible to remove the backing fabric and under-thread stitch to produce panels with only the tow steered preform. In the following sections three case studies are described which dealt with compression, buckling and bearing strength of tow steered CFRP panels.

CASE STUDY 1: COMPRESSION STRENGTH

Preform Manufacture

Tow steered preforms were produced in-house using an embroidery machine manufactured by Tajima GmbH. The unidirectional preforms were produced using IMS 5131 carbon fibre from Toho Tenax, 150 dtex Grilon MS stitching yarn with a suitable backing fabric. The preforms were 270mm x 180mm, with 7 ply UD fibre lay-up.

The laminates were manufactured using Hexcel's 914 resin film, used in a blocked form at the bottom of the ply stack, with a modified cure cycle, to produce the composite panels by resin film infusion. Various combinations of the design variables were used to produce stitched, partially stitched and folded preforms. For the folded preform varieties double width samples were produced which were then folded to make the required thickness. Calculated fibre volume fractions of the panels were around 51%. A total of six panels were produced.

Results and Discussion

All the panels were scanned using a through transmission Meccasonics C-Scanner. The scans showed relatively void-free panels, though one of the unstitched panel showed significant in-plane fibre distortion. Microscopic analysis was carried out to check the fibre crimp due to the in-plane and out-of-plane stitching. The micrographs showed less resin-rich area compared to the observations presented in Hazra and Potter [2] because of the use of thinner stitching yarn and needle. Further microscopic investigation of the surface tows showed in-plane crimp in the fibres (in all the panels) which occurred due to the shearing of the fibre bundle as it was steered round a corner and the displacement of the tow due to the through-thickness stitching [Fig. 2].

One unstitched panel was used for the compression testing. The Imperial College Method for Testing Composite Materials in Compression (ICSTM) was used to carry out the compression testing. The test coupons were cut using a CNC cutter and the end tabs (3mm thick, 10mm apart) were ground flat. The coupons were 90 mm long and 10 mm wide, while the gauge length including the adhesive fillet section was approximately 16 mm. The tests were conducted using a Zwick 1478, 100kN servo electric testing machine. The strength values were calculated using standard formula. One of the failed samples was scanned using a SkyScan 1174 MicroCT scanner, before and after compression testing, to analyse the final fracture locations.

As seen in the Fig. 2, use of soluble stitching yarn and removal of backing fabric led to fairly straight tow bundles with no stitch-heavy side of the panels. However, it must be pointed out that removal of backing fabric from a UD laminate is difficult, as these thin laminates could easily be damaged. Placement of resin-film block in the middle of the ply stack of the folded preform led to irregular resin-rich areas in the middle of the panel, a scenario that makes this technique not suitable (compared to the placement of the resin-film block at the bottom of the ply stack).

Fig. 2: Micrographs of the Tow Steered Panel

The average compression strength of the UD samples was 727 MPa (CV 13.9%) [Table 1]. However, strength value up to 920MPa was observed, indicating that higher compression strength is achievable in tow steered panels. The failure modes observed in the CT scan images showed different failure modes at the ends and centre, indicating possible local fibre architecture variations.

Table 1: Compression Properties of UD Tow Steered Panels

Test Sample	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Load (kN)	Strength (MPa)	Failure Location
UST1	10.06	2.22	-16.13	-722.2	Gauge
UST2	10.06	2.10	-15.76	-746.0	Gauge
UST3	10.06	2.08	-15.93	-761.3	Gauge
UST4	10.05	2.01	-12.14	-601.0	End Tab
UST5	10.02	2.29	-15.64	-681.6	Gauge
UST6	10.07	2.30	-21.32	-920.5	End Tab
UST7T	10.02	2.30	-15.2	-659.6	Gauge
			Average	-727.5	
			Std. Dev.	101.2	
			CV%	-13.9	

Based on the experimental results it can be concluded that the observed low compressive strength values of the UD tow steered panel could be due to misalignment of the in-plane fibre as they were unstitched, though out-of-plane crimp was reduced with the use of Grilon yarn. Longer gauge length may also have caused premature buckling during the test. Further investigations showed that without the use of telecentric lens measured strain values are affected by out-of-plane movement, indicating bending or misalignment of the test sample which leads to a reduction in the compressive strength as well as lead to invalid strain measurements.

CASE STUDY 2: POST BUCKING PERFORMANCE

Preform Manufacture

Preforms were manufactured using the same methodology described in case study 1. The preforms were 440mm x 230mm, with 8 ply variable stiffness lay-up. The details of the fibre directions in the variable stiffness lay-ups and the corresponding fibre volume fractions are listed in Table 2, where “a” represents the panel length in the x-direction and “b” the width in the y-direction and “X” the maximum angle of a tow. Final fibre trajectories are presented in Fig. 3.

In the design of Plate 2 and 4, the fibre at the centre of the plate begins with a 45° angle to the x-axis that linearly decreases in four equal sections to angles 33.75°, 22.5°, 11.25° and finally 0°. Plate 4 had longer 0° and 90° plies designed to achieve better post-buckling performance than Plate 2. In Plate 14 each tow contained a different maximum angle X. The fibre trajectories for the longitudinal plies begins with 0° at the edges with gradual increments of 0.5° up to an angle of 10.5°, thereafter the increments are in 0.7° up to the maximum value of 30.4°. This design could fit in adequately wide 0° fibres for high buckling and post-buckling performance. The angle increments and maximum angle were chosen to avoid large tow overlaps and to prevent the occurrence of large gaps. The minimum distance between the tows was 1.5mm whilst the maximum was 3.4mm. Transverse fibre directions were similar to the longitudinal except for some minor modifications. All these configurations were chosen to enhance the post-buckling performance.

Table 2: Tow Trajectories and V_f of the Panels

Plate	Lay-up		Global V_f
	Longitudinal	Transverse	
Baseline	-45/ +45 /0/ 90/90/0/+45/-45		68.0
Plate 2	$0_{\pm} < 45 33.75 22.5 11.25 0 (a/8) >$	$90_{\pm} < 45 33.75 22.5 11.25 0 (b/8) >$	67.8
Plate 4	$0_{\pm} < 45 22.5 0 0 0 (a/8) >$	$90_{\pm} < 45 22.5 0 0 0 (b/8) >$	67.6
Plate 14	$0_{\pm} < X 2X/3 X/3 0 0 (a/8) >$	$90_{\pm} < X 2X/3 X/3 0 0 (b/8) >$	66.6

One panel per design was produced, C-Scanned and the panel thickness variations were measured. The results showed low voids and small thickness variations despite large changes in fibre angle. The reliability of the results could have been greatly improved by testing a larger number of plates for each design or by carrying out a greater number of low load tests for a small number of panels.

Fig. 3: Tow Path Trajectories for the Variable Stiffness Plates

Results and Discussion

During the compression testing because of some misalignment of the panel ends, local bending stresses were generated which led to the failure of all the panels in the gap between the anti-buckling guide and its end plate.

Three measures of performance were used to determine the improvement of the variable stiffness panels upon the baseline: the magnitude of the critical buckling loads, the relative stiffness of the panels (the ratio before and after buckling) and their central out-of-plane deflection. The pre- and post-buckling results are shown in Table 3 and Fig 3. The results were normalised with respect to the baseline cross sectional area, as there were significant difference in the areas for Plates 4 and 14.

Table 2: Relative Experimental Stiffness Changes after Buckling

	Cross Sectional Area (mm ²)	Test Pre-buckled Stiffness (Nmm ⁻²)	Normalised Pre-buckled Stiffness (Nmm ⁻²)	Test Post-buckled Stiffness (Nmm ⁻²)	Normalised Post-buckled Stiffness (Nmm ⁻²)	Change
Baseline	536	19780	19780	14200	14200	-28.2%
Plate 2	543	19690	19465	14600	14433	-25.9%
Plate 4	547	18586	18219	14800	14508	-20.4%
Plate 14	610	21390	18831	19592	17248	-8.4%

The buckling loads of the three tow steered plates were higher than those of the baseline, because of the presence of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies at the panel centre and the concentration of cross-ply near the panel ends. The tow steered panels also demonstrated significantly improved post-buckling performance compared to the quasi-isotropic baseline. Plate 2 and 4 produced only small increments in post-buckled performance, because of the central $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, which were unable to carry axial stresses as the load increased after buckling. Plate 14 showed the highest post-buckling stiffness and the least reduction of stiffness after buckling. This higher stiffness indicates this plate's ability to continue to carry major compressive loads after buckling which can be attributed to the cross-ply that have more coverage around the panel. The high fibre volume fraction regions might also have acted as stiffeners and contributed to this increase in post-buckling stiffness.

Fig. 4: Normalised Stiffness Prior and After Buckling

The ratio of post-buckled to pre-buckled stiffness of Plate 14 was found to be 0.92 compared to 0.72 found for an equal weight quasi-isotropic plate. This 20% relative stiffness enhancement, 30% improvement in buckling load and reduced out-of-plane deflection demonstrates the potential improvements in structural efficiency that can be achieved using tow placement in variable stiffness laminates. Further augmentation of the buckling load for Plate 14 could have been achieved if $\pm 45^\circ$ tows were used in the panel centre, instead of 30.4° .

CASE STUDY 3: BOLT BEARING STRENGTH

Preform Manufacture

Preforms were manufactured using the same methodology described in case study 1. The preforms were 270 mm x 140mm, of 7 ply [+45|0|-45|90|-45|0|+45] lay-up for the baseline. The optimized tow panel had the tows steered in radial patterns around two 10mm diameter holes that are 80mm apart. The design for the tow steered preform with holes resembled the baseline, except that the holes were incorporated in all the plies as

shown in Fig. 5(a). The stitching pattern for 0° was modified to achieve the circular tow path required and that of the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° , known to carry bearing loads well, were the same as the baseline. For these plies the tow was simply steered to create a hole in the desired position. After panel manufacture the baseline panel was drilled using a tungsten carbide drill bit, while for the optimized tow steered panel the resin-rich zones in the holes were drilled out.

Fig. 5: (a) Preform Showing the 0° Ply with the Holes; (b) Test Fixture

Manufactured panels were 2.05mm thick with a fibre volume fraction of 56%. The panels were C-scanned, which showed low voids. Five samples each were tested for the baseline and the tow steered varieties.

Results and Discussion

The samples were tested in tension for bearing strength using a single bolt at either end, Fig. 5(b), until the specimen failed. During the test the failure load was chosen as the point where the load fell by at least 50N while the extension continued to increase. The samples were not loaded beyond this point to ensure bearing failure only. The experimental results showed a 50% increase in average bearing strength for the tow steered panel over the baseline (Fig. 6). A T-test for significance showed 80% probability that the difference was significant, indicating high scatter of the results. The reason could be because of misalignment between the hole and the bolt, and some fibre damage during the drilling of the holes.

Fractographic analysis was then carried out using dye penetrants and ultraviolet light to investigate the propagated cracks and delaminations in detail. Fig 7 shows the samples cut through the centre of the hole along the loading direction. The hole is on the right hand side of each picture, with the bearing failure in the centre. The damaged areas are shown as bright turquoise; while the resin and fibres are shown in light blue and dark blue respectively.

The optimized tow steered samples showed considerably less damage – some matrix cracking was visible which did not propagate far. Under further loading these samples would retain strength for longer than the baseline. This property is desirable for joint manufacture, as the joints would be able to carry load after failure whilst making the

design failsafe. If the joint could fail in bearing but still maintain most of its strength, it would need less maintenance and could save on costs.

Fig. 6: Bearing Failure Stresses for Tow Steered Samples

Fig. 7: Extent of Damage in the Tested Samples

CONCLUSIONS

Coupon level test results show the possible applications of the tow steering technology for the production of preforms to tailor desired mechanical properties. However, it must be borne in mind that the production speed of this technique is rather slow and therefore not suitable as a mainstream preform manufacturing technique. Tow steering should be

used where the part is under a small number of high loading cases. In such loading cases a complex fibre path would optimize the part design and would lead to a reduction in weight of the part. In many cases this technique can be used in conjunction with other types of preforms that can be used as a base material.

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